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Two Models for the Embedding of Somatic Mutations Using Drug Screening Datasets

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1 Background

The past decade has witnessed an explosion of health data, from large numbers of genomic sequences to electronic health records. This has fuelled the promise of a new era of precision medicine; allowing personalised strategies for prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases that take individual variability in genes and lifestyle into account. Machine learning models can achieve good performance even when based on simplistic models (Figure 1). For instance, the task of predicting disease phenotypes based on genotypic information has been successfully undertaken by several groups, showcasing the expressive power of neural networks, [1, 2].

Figure 1: Predictive model underlying black-box deep-learning approaches.

However, Machine learning (ML) algorithms continue to face serious challenges when unknown biological mechanisms are under investigation or when these tools are applied in a medical context. In the first instance, relating a ML model to biological processes requires interpretability and causal reasoning. For example, disease states are manifestations of complex hierarchically interacting cellular processes, mirrored by different layers of biological signals that can be acquired by state-of-the-art omics technologies (e.g., genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mechanistic model underlying the phenotype of a cell.

A particular diagnosed disease, such as cancer, can therefore arise through vastly different underlying causal pathways. Identifying the affected mechanisms in disease sub-classes is however crucial to identifying drug targets and to guide individual prognosis and therapeutic choices. For this reason, it may be necessary to break down the complexity of cell biology into several sub-problems to be solved while considering how the different parts of the biological processes fit together.

Additionally, particular difficulties arise when the application of ML tools intersects with socio-economic considerations, including data bias and fairness [3] as well as privacy trade-offs [4]. Precision medicine, with its potential consequences for diagnosis and treatment planning, requires careful considerations to ensure that the methodologies adopted will not affect negatively the people for whom these novel tools are developed. A proper understanding of the mechanistic structure of any machine learning model used for this application is therefore crucial before widespread adoption in the applied medical field.

Recently, deep-learning-based approaches have been successfully employed to learn representations of somatic mutations across different cancer types [5, 6]. While it has already been shown that these embeddings can be used for accurate classification and prediction tasks, lower-dimensional embeddings for somatic mutations may also yield interesting insights into the underlying mechanisms that drive disease development and progres-

sion. The aim of this project is, therefore, to connect somatic mutation embeddings with affected pathways and cellular phenotypes, such as cell growth, proliferation and apoptosis. Ultimately this insight will be used both for identifying novel drug targets and for making accurate predictions with respect to individual drug responses.

1.1 General Model of the Cellular Machinery

For this project, we base our research questions on a more comprehensive model of the cellular machinery, which is shown in Figure 2.

This model is not complete, as other complex mechanisms could be included for a more exhaustive description of the cell, but the added depth compared to the naive black-box models is a valuable tool.

The downside of such a complex model is the requirement for in-depth domain knowledge to design and validate the individual components that we study. The advantage is that the inclusion of biological information in the design information allows for more robust predictions, for which explainability and interpretability are not foregone in favour of the blind performance of a black-box model.

Analogous explanation models have been proposed in previous works in the literature, although with some variation depending on the final applications considered, which leads to highlighting or making implicit some factors. An example of this is shown in Figure 3, where the proposed model is tailored specifically for cancer diagnosis.

Figure 3: Genetic machinery model posed for applications to cancer diagnosis. Image from [7].

Many considerations can be made for determining the structure of this causal model, but most of the connections in the diagram can be justified by previous works in biological literature.

Germline variants can impact somatic mutations [8, 9], especially if the cellular repair machinery is affected, such as mutations of *TP53*.

Mutations, both due to somatic events and to germline variants, directly affect the epigenetic landscape of a cell by affecting DNA methyltransferases, or demethylases (TET enzymes), chromatin remodellers and other factors such as histones [10].

The transcriptome is affected by somatic and germline mutations through a variety of mechanisms [11, 12] including Transcription Factors (TF) alterations [13] and modifications to promoter regions and TF binding sites [14, 15].

Epigenetic changes, including histone modifications and DNA methylation, have been linked to tumorigenesis and cancer development [16, 17] and disease in general [18], which makes them a particularly compelling candidate for explicit modelling to gain insight into the mechanisms through which they negatively affect the cellular machinery.

Somatic mutations also affect signalling pathways, both through proteome-mediated effects [19] as well as direct kinase mutations [20].

Finally, most of the steps shown in the diagram of cellular machinery are affected by external factors, such as environment and exposure to carcinogens and drugs.

1.2 Colorectal Cancer

In this project, we will particularly study Colorectal cancer (CRC). It is well suited for the exploration of ML-based analysis methods as there are large repositories of germline and somatic mutations from tumour samples available (COAD-US¹, COCA-CN², International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC) [21]). In addition, the Colorectal Cancer Atlas provides extensive data on 178 well-studied cancer cell lines, including drug response assays. CRC is the third most diagnosed cancer and has the fourth highest mortality rate reported worldwide. While CRC diagnosis might be summarized with a single positive/negative value, understanding the changes that led to the tumorigenesis could provide valuable information for determining the optimal direction for a treatment plan. Only $\sim 5\%$ of its occurrences can be attributed to highly penetrant germline variants [22]. Commonly, the development of CRC is due to an accumulation of mutations in tumour suppressor genes and oncogenes [23]. The multistep nature of these carcinogenic processes makes it crucial to properly consider the trajectories of mutations that lead to different outcomes for different patients.

As an example, 35 to 45% of colorectal cancers have a mutated *KRAS* gene, which codes for a protein that regulates cell growth. Inhibiting the mutated form of *KRAS* may

¹<https://dcc.icgc.org/projects/COAD-US>

²<https://dcc.icgc.org/projects/COCA-CN>

provide a key to developing treatments for KRAS-positive cancers, but this challenge has eluded researchers for decades [24]. It was also hypothesised that a large fraction of CRC patients might respond to anti-epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) antibody therapy. However, KRAS and NRAS mutations have been identified as biomarkers of resistance to these drugs [25]. Proper understanding of these mutations and their effects on the associated MEK-ERK and PIK3CA-AKT pathways could therefore have invaluable benefits for various strategies to prevent, overcome or revert resistance to anti-EGFR moAbs. Importantly, mutations in KRAS occur in approximately 25% of all human cancers, including more than 90% of pancreatic cancers and approximately 25% of lung cancers. Lessons learnt from KRAS variants in CRC might therefore be translatable when learning pan-cancer somatic mutation embeddings.

Analysing how the changes to a single gene and their interaction with other cancer mutations might affect the signalling pathways and the cellular phenotype, as in the example in Figure 5, could therefore lead to improved therapeutic target selection and further motivates the approach presented in the following sections.

1.3 Drug Screening Data

The application of machine learning models to clinical data might be the most obvious candidate for the development of precision medicine approaches for cancer, however, the analysis of drug screening in cancer cell lines allows to build robust preclinical models to gain insights into the genomic diversity of human cancers [26].

Drug screening datasets offer a wealth of information that can be used to learn more about parts of the cellular machinery. With the widespread adoption of High-Throughput Screening (HTS) technologies, it has become possible to gather large amounts of data on various aspects of cellular biology, including genotypic information, transcriptomics, proteomics. Additionally, automated imaging strategies provide valuable phenotype responses on the cellular level. The complementary nature of these channels of data makes HTS data a particularly compelling candidate for the use of multi-view representation learning models [27].

As discussed above in the context of the KRAS gene, proper analysis of the nature and effect of biomarkers that characterise cancers is a powerful tool to be leveraged: in 2017, the FDA approved the first treatment based on tumour-site agnostic molecular aberration biomarkers [28]. Understanding the properties of biomarkers and their effect on phenotype and disease is a promising direction for the development of novel cancer therapies.

2 Proposed Methodology

For the embedding of somatic mutations, we propose to use drug screening datasets of isogenic cancer cell lines. The perturbations induced by gene knockouts and exposure

to drugs are valuable sources of information that allow us to gain insights into the contributions of somatic mutations in the overall model presented in Figure 2.

2.1 Dataset

The data used for the development of these methodologies is the Pharmacogenetic Phenome Compendium (PGPC) dataset [29]. It is a drug screen of HCT116 colon cancer cell lines for which 10 somatic mutations and over 1000 compounds were screened.

The mutations screened, as well as their role in the relevant cancer pathways, are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Cell lines used in the PGPC dataset. The use of isogenic cell lines derived from a cancer lines controls for the germline variants that could confound the analysis on these mutations. Image from [29].

The dataset includes 385 phenotypic features, including measures of nuclear and cellular shape and texture, which were extracted from the images of the cell cultures using the R package EBImage³. The dataset includes also information on chemical-genetic interactions that are useful to validate the performance of the model presented in Section 2.2.

This dataset was chosen both because of the rich information contained in the phenotypic features gathered for many drug-genotype combinations and because of the deeper considerations that can be made on the nature of the specific disease.

³<https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/EBImage.html>

Figure 5: Model of the effects of *KRAS* mutations. In the context of the general model in Figure 2, the "KRAS gene" and "MAPK signalling" boxes represent instances for "Somatic Mutations" and "Signalling" respectively.

2.2 Clustering-based Embedding

The first approach to encode the mutations is derived by applying unsupervised dimensionality reduction techniques and cluster analysis on the phenotypic features data. In this case, the underlying model is displayed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Model underlying the clustering approach for mutation embedding.

This model is obtained from the general model by controlling for germline variants (which is done through the use of isogenic cell lines), and considering as external factors only the drugs to which cell cultures were exposed. The general phenotype is represented by a cluster assignment, while all the intermediate steps are made implicit.

With this model, a mutation is represented by the probability mass function (PMF) over the cluster assignment and determines how likely it is for a certain mutation to "move" a sample to a certain cluster within the data space.

The initial motivation for this approach derives from the observation that mutations are the primary drivers in clustering patterns within certain datasets analysed. As an example, consider the clustering pattern revealed by a UMAP projection applied to the PGPC dataset displayed in Figure 7.

The aim of learning to represent mutations with this approach is to detect anomalies: with a probabilistic model it is possible to determine whether the cluster assignment for a sample is driven by its mutations or by the drug administered, and when neither factor can explain the experimental observation, then that sample constitutes a candidate for a genetic interaction between the drug and the mutation.

The advantage of this methodology, compared to previous approaches to genetic inter-

Figure 7: UMAP projection of phenotypic features contained in the PGPC dataset. The 12 cell lines are the primary drivers of the clustering pattern observed. A few samples, identified by the label *genotype + drug*, have been highlighted to show how the phenotypic features of the cells can vary significantly between clusters.

actions discovery found in the literature is that it is a non-parametric approach, which does not assume any specific functional form for the interaction, which are normally described as deviations from the expected additive behaviour of the separate contributions of mutations and drugs to the final phenotype. In this case, an interaction is described as an anomaly in the cluster assignment pattern, which neither the PMF representation of the mutation or the drug can explain. This makes the approach more flexible and robust while requiring fewer explicit assumptions. The inductive biases present in this methodology are hidden in the choice of dimensionality reduction and clustering algorithms, which can be selected and tuned to apply to specific datasets.

The second advantage of this method is that it does not impose any restriction on the features used for the clustering. As a consequence, it is a compelling possibility to apply

this model to features extracted from imaging data directly through the use of models such as CNNs, which allow for the extraction of richer feature sets compared to available software that extracts pre-defined features.

The specifics of the implementation for the application to the PGPC dataset are as follows:

1. Project the 385 phenotypic features to a lower dimensional space using UMAP [30].
2. Cluster the UMAP representation using HDBSCAN [31], to assign to each sample a label. The hyperparameters for the clustering algorithm are tuned to minimise the number of samples that are assigned with low probability to any cluster.
3. Estimate the marginal probability mass function for the cluster assignment for each mutation $P_m = p(K|\text{mut} = m) = \sum_{\text{drug}} p(K|\text{mut} = m, \text{drug}) p(\text{drug})$, where K indicates the cluster label.
4. Analogously calculate the probability mass function for the cluster assignment for each drug $P_d = p(K|\text{drug} = d) = \sum_{\text{mut}} p(K|\text{mut} = m, \text{drug} = d) p(\text{mut})$.
5. For each sample calculate the cross entropy between its one-hot-encoded cluster label and each of P_m and P_d . High loss in both cases indicates that neither one of these marginal distributions approximates well $p(K|\text{mut}, \text{drug})$, therefore we consider the sample a candidate for a drug-gene interaction.

The reason to consider comparisons to P_m and P_d separately is that in this dataset, as in most drug screens, the number of replicates is limited, in this case to 2. As there is no reliable way to estimate $p(K|\text{mut}, \text{drug})$ from just 2 samples, we limit ourselves to verifying how likely it is that the observed values come from either marginal conditional probability mass function.

The whole procedure is repeated for multiple randomization seeds to take into account the stochastic nature of UMAP, and the information on the replicates present in the dataset is used to further filter the candidates, by imposing consistency of cluster assignment between replicates. In the end, only combinations of drugs and mutations that show up as candidates in a percentage of the runs that is above a selected threshold (90%) are considered as true candidates. This information is then validated by examining the relevant literature on the specific mutations.

Representing mutations through PMFs for cluster assignment allows us to interpret the clusters themselves, and gain insight into the differences and similarities of the genotypes. Comparing the differences in phenotypic features between clusters that represent different mutations is a simple way to obtain an interpretable description of the average effect of a mutation on the phenotype.

Preliminary validation of this methodology applied to the PGPC dataset shows that this approach can successfully retrieve some gene-drug interactions described in the literature,

although further analysis is required to evaluate the performance and generalizability of this method.

2.3 Pathway-based Embedding

The second methodology to learn embeddings for mutations is based on the model shown in Figure 8. The rationale of this approach is to explicitly model the difference in phenotypic features between two samples which based on a mediator (the differential activation in the biological pathways), which is caused by the differences in mutations and drugs between the samples.

Figure 8: Model underlying the differential pathway approach for mutation embedding. The grey background for the differential pathway activations remarks that it is an un-observed state of the system.

As in the previous case, we obtain this model from the general one by controlling for germline variants and considering drugs as the only external factor. The main difference is that the signalling step is made explicit, while the target phenotype is limited to the cellular phenotype.

This model allows us to predict the differences in pathway activations for the various mutations compared to the parental (control) cell line, as well as for the different drugs compared to the control (DMSO). In turn, this model expresses explicitly the phenotypic effect of these differential activations on the phenotypic features that are ultimately observed. Modelling pathway activation allows for the determination of a drug's mode of action (MOA), as well as for a deeper understanding of the mechanism that mutations in specific genes cause.

The mechanistic nature of this model requires stronger assumptions in the design of the functions involved and requires prior knowledge to be leveraged to ensure the meaningfulness of these representations. Because of the latter, data on pathway membership was collected from the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes⁴ (KEGG) database [32], which gives a set of prior information to use as constraints for the model.

Knowledge of affected pathways is a promising tool for several applications ranging from drug repurposing to therapeutic drug target selection, which motivates the choices made for this model, despite the stronger assumptions required.

⁴<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>

This methodology has been implemented but it is not yet validated with data from the literature. The details of the implementation are as follows.

1. For each mutation in the dataset, information on pathway membership is collected from the KEGG GENES database.
2. For the drugs that are present in the KEGG DRUG database, information on targets is collected and used again to collect the pathways affected.
3. The union set of pathways constitutes the K -dimensional "activation" space for both mutations and drugs. The differential effect of a mutation or a drug compared to the control is represented by a K -dimensional vector of values that range from -1 to 1, each entry of which represents the level of differential activation or inhibition of a specific pathway.
4. Initialize a D -dimensional embedding for each mutation and drug.
5. Initialize a neural network $g : D \times D \rightarrow K$ that predicts the differential activation level based on the drug and the mutation.
6. Pre-train this function and the embeddings jointly using the pathway membership information collected at the beginning. This means that, for example, *control cell line + drug* should output non-zero entries only for the known pathways affected by the drug. The same can be said for the *mutation + control drug* samples, while the *parental cell line + control drug* samples should only output zeroes, as all the values are differential compared to the control.
7. Initialize a $F \times K$ dimensional matrix E where element E_{fk} represents the effect that the pathway k has on the phenotypic feature f (again, differential effect compared to the control sample). This matrix is used to calculate the predicted difference in phenotypic features $\Delta \mathbf{f} = E \Delta \mathbf{p}$, where $\Delta \mathbf{p}$ is the output of the neural network g .
8. Jointly train the neural network g and the matrix E using the squares error on the predicted differential features and gradient descent. During this training, the prior information collected from KEGG is used to enforce soft constraints on the loss function.

The joint training of the neural network and the pathway effect matrix can be split into sub-processes, in which we can freeze either of those elements or the embeddings and train the rest.

This model learns dense embeddings for the genotypes that can be used to analyse the somatic mutations more in detail. The prediction of differential pathway activation could be valuable to determine drug mode of action and understand the effect of the somatic mutation on the signalling pathways.

The validity of this model is currently being examined in detail.

3 Discussion and Future Work

This report presented a brief overview of the methodologies used to embed somatic mutations, as well as their limitations in that most of the approaches found in the literature rely on black-box modes which are not designed with domain knowledge in mind. A general model of the cellular machinery was presented, and it was used to derive two models for the embedding of somatic mutations through different assumptions.

In one case, cluster assignment prediction is used for anomaly detection which is a promising tool for the detection of drug-gene interactions. This allows us to gain insights into how the mutations are affected by different perturbations.

The second model attempts to explicitly model the effects of drugs exposure and somatic mutations on the regulation of the signalling pathways, with the promising application of predicting drug mode of action.

The next steps for this project begin with the systematic validation of the two models presented. The use of datasets with the inclusion of different sources of data (e.g. transcriptomics, proteomics) will allow us to design models that account for larger portions of the general cellular machinery models discussed previously and is the most promising approach to gain deep insight into the machine learning applications most suitable for precision medicine.

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